

Online Hostel Room Booking System

Allocate Room in Hostel Booking System

¹Pradnya Raibhan, ²Pranavi Khandagale, ³Balkrishna Patil, ⁴Taranpreet Ruprah

^{1,2,3}Student, ⁴Assistant Professor,

¹Computer Science and Engineering Department,

¹Rajarambapu Institute Of Technology, Sangli, India

Abstract:- This Paper manages some operations in the hostel. The number of educational establishments has been increasing steadily over the past few years. As a consequence, there are more dormitories available to accommodate students on campus. Because the hostel manager has already turned on the software, it is usually not used in this situation. This project mainly addresses the challenges of running an inn and rooms without the problems that arise while carrying out tasks manually. After reviewing the deficiencies of the current system, a properly constructed computer system that will work with it is designed. System defects may be corrected by increasing the efficiency of the system. This project combines the transactional administration of college residences for better monitoring and more timely responses. Time lags and marked-paper transactions are thereby eliminated.

Keywords:- Student-Login, Hostel-Manager/AdminLogin, Register Page, Student/Hostel-Owner Registration, Student/Hostel-Owner Homepage, Online Hostel Room Booking.

I. INTRODUCTION

The system of hostel room management was created with their collaboration to assist the room management team in keeping track of information on the students' rooms and other things. The capacity to locate student records and information on those who have previously dropped classes is the key advantage of this technique. To view the data of all the students who have gotten and registered their hostel forms, you only need to log in as the administrator. Click verify to determine their eligibility and place them in the appropriate hostel. The assumption behind this solution was that the hostel room management staff wouldn't require such a capable individual to oversee and control the actions of the students in the hostel. We can eliminate the shortcomings of the current management by increasing the effectiveness of the hostel room management. Students may self-reserve rooms and make payments via this website or mobile application. Student data is safely stored on this website. This web portal assists in tracking and assigning room housekeeping, improving performance and accuracy, and notifying users when their room is prepared. Through this app, the housekeeping manager is continually informed about housekeeping tasks. The selected room or seat is recorded by a hostel booking engine as evidence that a guest has reserved it. Payment can be made at the time of booking or when a guest checks into a hostel. A customer can do this quickly and easily by using a credit card and hostel booking software. The electronic check from the client is

evidence that the service has been paid for. A hostel seat booking system that is now taken for granted by the majority of consumers offers them certain advantages over the reservation services they can get on arrival. Hostel management systems are used to oversee daily operations and do other essential administrative duties.

II. RELATED WORK

[1] D. Bikash Choudhary et al. developed the PHP-MySQL source code, which may be used to compose the system based on hostel management. It minimizes work put in by the hostel manager and chief when operating the hostel. It does away with the pen-and-paper method that we have used in the past. Data from the established context are provided, including information about hostels, their rooms, and their accounts, in addition to providing a solution for manual hostel management concerns.

[2] D. S. A. Braimah et al expected E-registrations border, updating the student endeavors/ Doormen's work was anything but challenging. The needed registration process stages must be reduced to the fewest number of steps possible if the system is to be rapid, effective, and appropriate. Paper-based registration procedures take a lot of time and cost money. 1. Decreased the amount of paperwork and duplication, increasing productivity. 2. Help the hostel manage its data and integrate the profiles of its students. 3. Cite the statistics on the demand for students from the hostel (e.g., tables, chairs, etc.). 4. Aid the hostel in easily giving student accounts at any moment.

[3] Christoph Jechlitschek presents a study on radio frequency identification (RFID) technology. These labels first took the place of barcode scanners in supply chains. A tiny relay is an RFID tag that transmits a serial number or another sort of identifier when a reader asks them to do so. The two most important components of RFID are the tag and the antenna. A transmitter and receiver are built into tags. The way an RFID tag operates is that the RFID device's receiver emits electromagnetic radiation, which causes the tag's antenna to conduct current. The paper examined the RFID gadget. RFID technology has a great chance of becoming widely used shortly. It is currently successfully used in inventory network administration to track.

[4] Felke-Morris says about security is currently one of the biggest problems people are dealing with on a global scale in all facets of their lives. Any organization values its information as its most valuable asset. The protection of sensitive information is a crucial evaluation criterion for any

level of affiliation. Databases are vulnerable to a variety of threats in the current world. The main security issues that databases have to deal with are outlined in this paper, and several encryption solutions that can lower the threat of attacks and safeguard sensitive data are covered. To reduce security threats, each group needs to have a security strategy that is adequately implemented.

III. SYSTEM ARCHITECTURE

A system architecture is a conceptual model that depicts the structure, behavior, and points of view of a system. To make it simpler to examine a system's component pieces and behavior, its architecture is formalized and represented. It is made up of developed system components and subsystems that work together to implement the whole system.

Fig 1: System Architecture

IV. PROPOSED SYSTEM

Hostel owners will be compelled to adapt the paper to their needs by using a reservation system. They will be able to add modules in accordance with the business rules. In addition to other categories, they can separate hostels into male, female, PG, and guest rooms. They can choose the cost and bed configuration for each hostel. Any hostel's owner can classify the beds as single, double, triple, etc. The payment status and payment details for each hostel are

accessible with a single click. In this way, users will be able to learn about the hostel's facilities and service charges for particular room types. Users will have the opportunity to add additional amenities, such as laundry, a mess, a saloon, etc. for their particular profile. The payment method, the total amount paid, the date, and time of the payment, as well as any applicable taxes and other fees, will all be made clear to users in their payment statement.

V. RESULT

Fig. 2: Student Login

Fig. 3: Hostel-Manager/Admin Login

Fig. 4: Register Page

Fig. 5: Student/Hostel-owner registration

Fig. 6: Student/Hostel-owner home page

Finally, we have created a safe, user-friendly hostel administration system for the online hostel room booking system. This system can take care of every member, whether they are a student or a hostel owner. With the help of this technology, they could effectively run their hostel. Each student receives a student ID and password, making the

system completely secure and removing any chance of unauthorized access. When mess, room booking, and cancellation are chosen, it is easier to utilize. Therefore, implementing this strategy will help to reduce labor costs while also offering students more reasons to like the hostel and keep coming back.

Fig. 7: Process of room booking

VI. CONCLUSION

A secure, user-friendly hostel administration system that is integrated with the online hotel room booking system has been developed for us. This system may take care of any member, whether they are a student or a hostel owner. With the help of this technology, they can properly run their hostel. This method is completely safe because each student is given a unique student ID and password, eliminating any chance of illegal access. Utilizing this technology can help reduce labor expenses and provide extra facilities so that students will appreciate the hostel and come back often. In a nutshell, the project built with HTML, PHP, JavaScript, and MySQL is based on a study into the existing framework and the needs of the user, with space for future improvement. For the current programming to function successfully, the proper approach to programming advancement is required. This website can be used for hostel administration by those who need to oversee various hostel operations. There are more schools, institutions, and students than ever before, thus we need an automated system that can lessen the amount of human labor required for administration while also making it easier and more technologically advanced.

FUTURE WORK

Thanks to our system, which is incredibly helpful for them, students may select their room according to their preferences and easily search for hostels in their neighborhood. Using this system, the hostel owner can store all the information regarding the students, their mess, etc. The thing might sell for less money if there aren't many bidders, which would imply the seller wouldn't get the best price. Potentially, buyers are unaware of the time of the auction. because the seller could start an auction at any time. Vendors and customers must both be mobile-friendly. The program won't be easy to use for someone who doesn't know how to use a mobile device. Users who wish to access the auction and buy or sell products must be connected to the internet because it is done online. We do not have GPS capability in our system. We'll continue to work on it.

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